

Species' climate niche modeling framework Predicting historical & future species' spatial distributions & estimation of species' thermal tolerance

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I. Objectives

The objective of this document is to provide the detailed framework developed and used in the Biodiversa/Belmont Forum SOMBEE project, and subsequently used in the European H2020 FutureMares and TriAtlas projects, and the Pew DUOS project. The framework has two main goals:

- To predict historical and future species' climate suitability, using climate niche models (cf. also called species distribution models; Figure 1-A). Climate niche models, relying on Hutchinson's (1957) conceptualization of a species niche, link observed species occurrences in space and time with ecologically meaningful environmental variables (among which climate variables play a predominant role; Sunday, Bates, and Dulvy 2011), to fit statistical relationships between them and predict species spatial distributions at different time and space combinations. For accurate calibration of the niche models, it is necessary to obtain a comprehensive description of the species responses to the environmental variables. Indeed, a model calibrated at a local scale only leads to an incomplete approximation of the niche that can reduce the predictive capacities of the models (Thuiller et al. 2004). Henceforth, we used two common environmental variables available at global scale, temperature and salinity, to calibrate species climate niches over the whole range of the variability of the environmental conditions where the species is present globally and to predict its climate niche' spatial distribution (Figure 1 : A-1).

- To characterize the thermal tolerance limits (critical thermal limits for survival : minimum and maximum temperatures) and the temperature that maximizes species' presence (thermal optimum). Indeed, climate niche models will be used to fit and visualize the species presence probability as a function of used climate variables, called 'prediction curves' or 'response curves' (Figure 1 : A-3). Elith et al., (2006) proposed a method to investigate response curves from differing statistical methods, which consists of making predictions at regular intervals over the range of the variable of interest while holding other variables constant (i.e. mean, min or max). Applying this technique allows to construct the thermal response curve which rises slowly from a lower critical temperature up to an optimum value of maximum presence, and then rapidly declines towards the upper critical temperature. These critical temperatures are required for the parameterization of the bioenergetic ecosystem model Bioen-OSMOSE (Morell et al. 2023).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the species distribution modeling framework. The figure illustrates the four stages of analysis proposed in the study. The methodology described in the present study is shown on the right (A- Niche modeling). A-1: Models' calibration : matching species occurrences with global historical climate data to determine the specific climate conditions under which a species can be found. A-2: Historical species distribution maps : predicted for each of the 9 pre-defined depth layers, through a specific study area. A-3: Species thermal tolerance : estimated with climate niche models by analyzing the temperatures that determine species' occurrence and finding the range of conditions within which the species occurs. A-4: Future projections of species distributions maps : projected for each of the 9 depth layers using downscaled and bias-corrected Earth System Model outputs (B).

II. Data

II.1 Species data

These data were assembled to predict species' spatial distribution in the 6 case studies of the SOMBEE project: North Sea, Gulf of Lions, Black Sea, West Coast of Canada, Northern Humboldt, Yellow Sea. For a total of 157 marine species (e.g. fish, marine mammals; Table 1), we extracted the vertical habitat of species (e.g. benthic pelagic, demersal) and their depth range (defined by a maximum and minimum depths) from global databases, notably, from FishBase and SeaLifeBase.

The biogeographic occurrences of the species (i.e. geographic locations) used in climatic niche modeling were obtained from 4 global databases:

OBIS (Ocean Biogeographic Information System) <http://www.iobis.org/>

GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility) <http://www.gbif.org/>

VertNet (vertebrate biodiversity networks) <http://vertnet.org/>

Ecoengine (UC Berkeley's Natural History Data) <https://ecoengine.berkeley.edu/>

These data have been rigorously filtered by removing potentially erroneous occurrences (e.g. located on continents) and keeping only observations made from 1993. These occurrences have been completed with regional survey data, when available, such as MEDITS (1994-2019) and PELMED (1994-2019) for the species of the Mediterranean sea.

II.2 Historical climate data

Monthly temperature and salinity between 1993 and 2018 were acquired from the latest Mercator Ocean reanalysis dataset ([link to the reanalysis product](#)) produced in the framework of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/>). The reanalysis (Global Ocean Reanalysis and Simulations : glorys12v1) is run at eddy-permitting resolution (1/12° horizontal resolution) and, importantly, assimilates available data from satellites and *in situ* platforms (e.g., ships, moorings, buoys) to provide robust climate information. Vertical structure in the reanalysis is resolved by 50 vertical layers from 0 m to an undersea depth of 5274 m (Figure 2).

II.3 Future climate data

To provide projections of future species distributions under climate change, we used two Earth System Models (ESMs) included in the latest generation of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6) : IPSL-CM6A-LR developed by the Institut Pierre Simon Laplace in France, and GFDL-CM4 developed by the Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory in the US. Both models

simulate the ocean's salinity and temperature that we used to make projections of future climate change under different greenhouse gas emission scenarios.

The spatial resolution of these future climate projections is typically coarser (1°) than that of the historical climate data used to calibrate niche models ($1/12^\circ$), and this can result in biased projections, particularly in study areas with strong environmental gradients. In addition, systematic biases in ESMs outputs are reported when compared to observations, and thus bias correction of ESM outputs is necessary for impact studies for which the absolute scale of the variable is as important as its trends (Oliveros-Ramos et al. 2023).. One approach to address this issue is to use statistical downscaling, which involves modeling the bias between historical data of the ESMs and observational data used for the niche modeling calibration, and correcting the ESM data for each study area (Figure 1-B). By generating more accurate estimates of the local climate conditions that are relevant to each study area, downscaling can help to improve the accuracy and reliability of species distribution models and their projections of future distributions under climate change (Figure 1-B).

Many downscaling studies focus on the surface layer of the ocean because it is easier to obtain data for that layer, and because many pelagic species inhabit this surface layer. However, for benthic or demersal species that inhabit different depth layers, it is important to downscale data for those layers as well. A simplified approach to this is to use a 3D downscaling method, which involves taking into account the vertical structure of temperature and salinity data for each location and time period, and using those profiles to estimate conditions at different depths.

Figure 2. Diagram of ocean layers defined differently depending on data source, and the simplified 9 at-depth layers defined for the study.

The observed historical data (Copernicus, Mercator) has 55 vertical layers; IPSL and GFDL models defined 75 and 50 layers, respectively. We defined nine simplified at-depth layers to reflect species' vertical habitats: [0-25m], [25-50m], [50-100m], [100-150m], [150-200m], [200-300m], [300-500m], [500-1000m], [1000-bottom]

In order to use a simplified approach to downscaling for different depth layers, the vertical layers of both the ESMs and "observed data" (used for the calibration of climate models) can be aggregated into 9 simplified at-depth layers (Figure 2). Downscaling, and projections of species distributions can then be generated for each of these depth layers separately. This approach allows for a more realistic representation of the conditions experienced by species at different depths, as opposed to only focusing on the surface layer of the ocean.

III. Calibration

Calibration is an important step in the development of species distribution models because it helps to ensure that the model is accurate and can be used to make reliable predictions. Model calibration begins with matching each species occurrence point to its temperature and salinity values (Figure 1 : A-1). In our study, the spatio-temporal resolution of the vertical structure of climate data has the advantage of allowing us to consider the vertical structure of the water column when matching species occurrences to climate data values (unlike remotely sensed data). Yet, species occurrence data are not vertically informed, such as fisheries catch data where there is no available information on the depth of catch. One approach to address the lack of depth information in species occurrence data is combining species occurrence data with knowledge about species ecology, such as the maximum and minimum depths limits, to assign the occurrence to a climate value for the depth-range where the species has been observed. To do this, for each species' occurrences, the corresponding temperature (and salinity) values were calculated by averaging their values over the layers that correspond to species' depth range (Table 1). For benthic species, only the bottom layer has been considered (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of temperature maps calculated to match-up species occurrences (green dots) in July 1993 (C°)

- (1) Top: the average temperature of the first 18 depth layers for a benthopelagic species (here brown shrimp: *Crangon crangon*) distributed vertically between 0 and -50 m
- (2) Bottom: the bottom temperature for a benthic species (here The European plaice: *Pleuronectes platessa*).

Because biological scientific surveys often cover areas of interest for fishing activities, the frequency of species occurrence may be higher in fishing areas, suggesting incorrectly that species are more abundant in those regions, which can potentially influence the results of climate niche models. To reduce this potential sampling bias, the occurrences were filtered before the calibration of the models following Beaugrand et al. 2011. We created a virtual bi-dimensional grid called environmental background at a resolution of 0.1°C (temperature) \times 0.1 psu (salinity), that covers the range of temperature and salinity values experienced by each species over time and throughout the depth layers that are encompassed within its depth range (called hereafter background limits; Figure 4). The geographic occurrences of a species are then projected onto the grid based on their respective temperature and salinity values. In cases where there are multiple occurrences of a species within a given temperature and salinity interval, only one occurrence is preserved (Schickele et al., 2020). This helps to reduce the potential bias introduced by having multiple occurrences in a small area, to avoid over-representing areas where sampling occurred more frequently, and instead focus on undersampled areas where the climate conditions are suitable for a given species.

Figure 4. Example of the background space used for *Sprattus sprattus* : the combinations of temperatures and salinities observed within a species' vertical depth range (0 to -150m) appear in black, the cells with the species' presence appear in green ; the white rectangle within the black area represents the "core niche" area (see text); the cells in red represent the pseudo-absences created randomly in number equal to the presences. They stand outside the convex envelope surrounding the the 1st and 99th quantiles of the cells containing presences.

The niche modeling approaches can be categorized into two groups: presence-only models vs. presence-absence models. These latter require both presence and absence data and perform better than presence-only models which are often overly optimistic (Barbet-Massin et al., 2012). As no confirmed absence data are available, especially for mobile species, artificial absence data typically called pseudo-absences are generated and used for the calibration of presence-absence models in lieu of confirmed absence (Schickele et al., 2020). Following Ben Rais Lasram et al. (2020), the pseudo-absences were generated randomly within species' environmental background space but only outside the convex hull polygon surrounding the 1st and 99th quantiles of the crossed intervals of temperature and salinity with presence previously filtered, excluding the "core niche" area and thus avoiding potential false absences (see Figure 4; Schickele et al., 2020). The number of generated pseudo-absences is also an important issue as an unbalanced design where there are more pseudo-absence points than presence points affect (positively or negatively) the performance of some models, introducing a bias in designs that involve multiple models. Therefore, we generated pseudo-absences in an equal number as filtered presences (see Figure 4), relying on the statistical theory known as "model-based designs" (Hengl et al. 2009).

Once the occurrences have been filtered and the pseudo-absences have been simulated, a set of models is constructed through a consensus approach to models (Araújo and New 2007). To do this, seven presence/absence based models were used, belonging to four main categories of models: multiple regressions (Generalized Linear Model, Generalized Additive Model), regression trees (Random Forest, Classification Tree Analysis), Flexible Discriminant Analysis and learning methods (Artificial Neural Network and Generalized Boosting Models). These algorithms were implemented using the R-package BIOMOD2 multi-model platform (Thuiller et al., 2016).

IV. Validation

All models were evaluated using a cross-validation procedure with random partitioning of occurrences (3-fold cross validation, hereafter "runs"). For each subset of data, 75% of the occurrences were used for calibration and the remaining 25% for validation. The predictive power of the models was evaluated using the True Skill Statistic (TSS; Allouche et al., 2006) and the Continuous Boyce Index (CBI; Hirzel et al. 2006), a metric specifically designed for presence-only models and insensitive to pseudo-absences.

Figure 5. Boxplot of the predictive performance (CBI scores) of all calibrated climate models for *Eledone cirrhosa*.

To improve the accuracy and robustness of predictive models, we used the “model averaging” method, that combine the predictions of multiple models to produce a final, consensus prediction that is more reliable than any individual model. Models with great predictive performance (i.e CBI greater than 0.5 ; Figure 5) were selected and weighted by their TSS, thus representing a central tendency across different models predictions (called “*model averaging*”). The climatic suitability map produced with the *model averaging* was then transformed into presence/absence maps using the probability threshold that maximized the TSS score of the 7 algorithms (Thuiller et al. 2009). We used the *model averaging* to predict both historical and future distributions for each species, as they can help to smooth out noise and errors in the input data and produce more accurate predictions.

V. Projections of species climatic niche

The third spatial dimension (i.e. the depth range of each species) is often overlooked when predicting and projecting future species distributions. For example, predicted distributions of benthic species generated using surface predictors will be inaccurate and will substantially change when depth-specific climate data are used. We used the *model averaging* for each modeled species to provide 3D climate suitability maps, represented as raster stacks for the all modeled depth-layers across the region of interest (Duffy & Chown, 2017, Bentlage, et al, 2013; Figure 6).

Figure 6. Monthly predicted climate suitability of *Sprattus sprattus* in the *Gulf of Lions* (Oct 2011), for the four simplified at-depth layers included in its depth range limits (0-150 m ; Table 1), modeled using *model averaging* approach. On the right, the presence/absence maps are derived from climate suitability maps, using the optimal threshold. Colors are ranged between yellow for presences, purple for absences.

Niche modeling in the marine realm could be limited because of the scarcity of some important predictor variables to determine the presence of a species such as dissolved oxygen (Ready et al., 2010). In fact, dissolved oxygen is crucial for the development and performance of many marine organisms (Woods and Moran, 2008). Constrained by the absence of a suitable biogeochemical dataset at global scale that integrates a data assimilation scheme, we used a mechanistic approach called Aerobic Scope Models (ASM) to estimate the species' aerobic scope (related to growth and used as a proxy of the general conditions of an organism) from species' thermal preference curves (Teal et al., 2018). This approach allowed species' presence probabilities maps (estimated with global climate data without oxygen) to be corrected taking into account local data of dissolved oxygen. The resulting maps thus capture the effects of multiple climate drivers (Salinity, temperature, and O₂).

VI. Estimation of the thermal tolerance limits and optimum

To build a species' thermal response curve, the salinity was held constant at its mean value of species' salinity background limits (relative to its vertical depth range), whilst the temperature was varied from the minimum value for species' temperature background limits to the maximum using a 0.1°C step. The variation in climate niche predictions made for these values only reflects the effects of variation in temperature (Elith et al., 2006). Representing these predicted species' presence probabilities as response to temperatures allows to construct species' thermal response curve (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The thermal response curve has typically a unimodal shape and represents the species' presence probability as a function of temperature which increases relatively slowly up to T_{opt} , and decreases above. CT_{min} and CT_{max} : lower and upper thermal limit of species presence, respectively (i.e. probabilities higher than the threshold).

The species' optimum temperature (T_{opt}) is calculated as the temperature corresponding to the maximal presence probability value (or mean temperature when the curve reaches a plateau; see figure x).

The Critical Temperatures (CT) which reflect survival limits for a species correspond to temperature bounds within which the species is present (CT_{min} and CT_{max} corresponding to the presence probabilities that are higher than the threshold defined in the validation procedure ; see figure 7).

Table 1 : List of 157 species selected for analysis for all study areas in SOMBEE. The species depth zone, and depth ranges (meters) provided from FishBase and SeaLifeBase. GL: Gulf of Lions (Mediterranean Sea), NS: North Sea, BS: Black Sea, HUM: Humboldt, WCC: West Coast of Canada, YS: Yellow Sea.

	<i>Species</i>	<i>Study area</i>	<i>Depth zone</i>	<i>Minimum depth</i>	<i>Maximum depth</i>
1	<i>Sardina pilchardus</i>	GL	pelagic-neritic	10	100
2	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	GL	pelagic-neritic	0	400
3	<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>	GL	pelagic-neritic	10	150
4	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	GL	pelagic-neritic	0	1050
5	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	GL	pelagic-neritic	0	1000
6	<i>Micromesistius poutassou</i>	GL	benthopelagic	150	3000
7	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	GL	demersal	30	1075
8	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	GL	demersal	10	328
9	<i>Illex coindetii</i>	GL	Pelagic	0	1000
10	<i>Octopus vulgaris</i>	GL	reef-associated	0	347
11	<i>Eledone cirrhosa</i>	GL	benthic	5	500
12	<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	GL	Pelagic	0	985
13	<i>Lophius budegassa</i>	GL	benthic	70	1013
14	<i>Spicara smaris</i>	GL	pelagic-neritic	15	328
15	<i>Spicara maena</i>	GL	pelagic-neritic	30	130
16	<i>Galeus melastomus</i>	GL	demersal	55	1873
17	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	GL	demersal	10	780
18	<i>Nephrops norvegicus</i>	GL	benthic	20	800
19	<i>Aristeus antennatus</i>	GL	benthic	100	2200
20	<i>Clupea harengus</i>	NS	benthopelagic	0	364
21	<i>Scomber scombrus</i>	NS	pelagic-neritic	0	1000
22	<i>Ammodytes marinus</i>	NS	benthopelagic	1	150
23	<i>Ammodytes tobianus</i>	NS	demersal	1	150
24	<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>	NS	pelagic-neritic	10	150
25	<i>Trisopterus esmarkii</i>	NS	benthopelagic	50	300
26	<i>Pleuronectes platessa</i>	NS	benthic	0	200
27	<i>Solea solea</i>	NS	benthic	0	150
28	<i>Pollachius virens</i>	NS	demersal	37	364
29	<i>Gadus morhua</i>	NS	benthopelagic	0	600
30	<i>Melanogrammus aeglefinus</i>	NS	demersal	10	450
31	<i>Trachurus trachurus</i>	NS	pelagic-neritic	0	1050
32	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	NS	benthopelagic	10	200
33	<i>Limanda limanda</i>	NS	benthic	20	150
34	<i>Eutrigla gurnardus</i>	NS	demersal	10	340
35	<i>Merluccius merluccius</i>	NS	demersal	30	1075
36	<i>Crangon crangon</i>	NS	benthopelagic	0	50
37	<i>Engraulis encrasicolus</i>	BS	pelagic-neritic	0	400
38	<i>Sprattus sprattus</i>	BS	pelagic-neritic	10	150
39	<i>Trachurus mediterraneus</i>	BS	pelagic-oceanic	0	500
40	<i>Mullus barbatus</i>	BS	demersal	10	328
41	<i>Merlangius merlangus</i>	BS	benthopelagic	10	200
42	<i>Scophthalmus maoticus</i>	BS	demersal	10	150
43	<i>Pomatomus saltatrix</i>	BS	pelagic-oceanic	0	200
44	<i>Sarda sarda</i>	BS	pelagic-neritic	80	200
45	<i>Euphausia mucronata</i>	HUM	pelagic	0	300
46	<i>Engraulis ringens</i>	HUM	pelagic-neritic	3	80
47	<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	HUM	pelagic-neritic	0	200
48	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	HUM	pelagic-neritic	0	300
49	<i>Trachurus murphyi</i>	HUM	pelagic-oceanic	10	306

50	<i>Pleuroncodes monodon</i>	HUM	epipelagic	0	40
51	<i>Dosidicus gigas</i>	HUM	pelagic	0	1200
52	<i>Merluccius peruanus</i>	HUM	bathydemersal	50	500
53	<i>Otaria byronia</i>	HUM	surface	0	175
54	<i>Vinciguerria lucetia</i>	HUM	benthopelagic	100	500
55	<i>Arctocephalus australis</i>	HUM	surface	0	150
56	<i>Euphausia pacifica</i>	WCC	pelagic	100	1000
57	<i>Clupea pallasii pallasii</i>	WCC	pelagic-neritic	0	475
58	<i>Atheresthes stomias</i>	WCC	demersal	18	950
59	<i>Gadus chalcogrammus</i>	WCC	benthopelagic	30	1280
60	<i>Gadus macrocephalus</i>	WCC	demersal	10	1380
61	<i>Ophiodon elongatus</i>	WCC	demersal	0	475
62	<i>Hippoglossus stenolepis</i>	WCC	demersal	0	1200
63	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	WCC	demersal	0	250
64	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	WCC	benthopelagic	0	375
65	<i>Phoca vitulina</i>	WCC	surface	0	355
66	<i>Eumetopias jubatus</i>	WCC	surface	0	250
67	<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>	WCC	surface	0	616
68	<i>Merluccius productus</i>	WCC	pelagic-neritic	0	1000
69	<i>Sebastes alutus</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	0	825
70	<i>Squalus acanthias</i>	WCC	benthopelagic	0	1460
71	<i>Microstomus pacificus</i>	WCC	demersal	10	1370
72	<i>Eopsetta jordani</i>	WCC	demersal	0	550
73	<i>Sebastes flavidus</i>	WCC	reef-associated	0	549
74	<i>Sebastes reedi</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	137	375
75	<i>Sebastes ruberrimus</i>	WCC	reef-associated	15	549
76	<i>Hydrolagus colliei</i>	WCC	demersal	0	913
77	<i>Anoplopoma fimbria</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	175	2740
78	<i>Thaleichthys pacificus</i>	WCC	pelagic-neritic	0	300
79	<i>Metacarcinus magister</i>	WCC	benthic	0	360
80	<i>Pandalus jordani</i>	WCC	benthic	36	457
81	<i>Bothrocara brunneum</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	129	2570
82	<i>Bothrocara molle</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	60	2688
83	<i>Bothrocara pusillum</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	55	642
84	<i>Lepidopsetta bilineata</i>	WCC	demersal	0	575
85	<i>Parophrys vetulus</i>	WCC	demersal	0	550
86	<i>Psettichthys melanostictus</i>	WCC	demersal	1	325
87	<i>Glyptocephalus zachirus</i>	WCC	demersal	0	900
88	<i>Hippoglossoides elassodon</i>	WCC	demersal	0	1050
89	<i>Isopsetta isolepis</i>	WCC	demersal	20	425
90	<i>Pleuronichthys decurrens</i>	WCC	demersal	8	533
91	<i>Platichthys stellatus</i>	WCC	demersal	0	375
92	<i>Citharichthys sordidus</i>	WCC	demersal	0	549
93	<i>Limanda aspera</i>	WCC	demersal	0	700
94	<i>Lyopsetta exilis</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	25	800
95	<i>Pleuronichthys coenosus</i>	WCC	demersal	18	350
96	<i>Sebastes brevispinis</i>	WCC	demersal	0	375
97	<i>Sebastes entomelas</i>	WCC	pelagic-neritic	0	549
98	<i>Sebastes paucispinis</i>	WCC	reef-associated	0	476
99	<i>Sebastes pinniger</i>	WCC	demersal	0	838
100	<i>Sebastes aleutianus</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	25	900
101	<i>Sebastes proriger</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	12	425
102	<i>Sebastes zacentrus</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	26	476
103	<i>Sebastes babcocki</i>	WCC	demersal	49	625

104	<i>Sebastolobus altivelis</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	201	1757
105	<i>Sebastes diploproa</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	0	800
106	<i>Sebastolobus alascanus</i>	WCC	demersal	17	1600
107	<i>Sebastes crameri</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	25	600
108	<i>Sebastes borealis</i>	WCC	bathydemersal	0	1200
109	<i>Sebastes maliger</i>	WCC	demersal	0	274
110	<i>Sebastes caurinus</i>	WCC	demersal	10	183
111	<i>Sebastes nigrocinctus</i>	WCC	reef-associated	10	275
112	<i>Sebastes nebulosus</i>	WCC	reef-associated	3	128
113	<i>Ammodytes hexapterus</i>	WCC	benthopelagic	0	275
114	<i>Cancer productus</i>	WCC	benthic	0	90
115	<i>Pandalus borealis</i>	WCC	benthopelagic	9	1450
116	<i>Pandalus dispar</i>	WCC	benthopelagic	45	649
117	<i>Pandalus platyceros</i>	WCC	benthic	0	2648
118	<i>Amphioctopus fangsiao</i>	YS	benthic	0	150
119	<i>Trachysalambria curvirostris</i>	YS	benthic	13	300
120	<i>Octopus variabilis</i>	YS	demersal	1	200
121	<i>Ammodytes personatus</i>	YS	demersal	0	172
122	<i>Konosirus punctatus</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	100
123	<i>Chelidonichthys spinosus</i>	YS	demersal	25	615
124	<i>Portunus trituberculatus</i>	YS	demersal	0	50
125	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	YS	benthopelagic	3	825
126	<i>Sardinella zunasi</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	5	100
127	<i>Saurida elongata</i>	YS	demersal	20	100
128	<i>Sardinops sagax</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	200
129	<i>Platycephalus indicus</i>	YS	reef-associated	20	200
130	<i>Thamnaconus septentrionalis</i>	YS	demersal	7	120
131	<i>Nibea albiflora</i>	YS	benthopelagic	25	80
132	<i>Sebastes schlegelii</i>	YS	demersal	3	100
133	<i>Pennahia argentata</i>	YS	benthopelagic	20	140
134	<i>Clupea pallasii pallasii</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	475
135	<i>Pennahia macrocephalus</i>	YS	demersal	0	100
136	<i>Scomberomorus niphonius</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	200
137	<i>Trichiurus lepturus</i>	YS	benthopelagic	0	589
138	<i>Engraulis japonicus</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	400
139	<i>Larimichthys polyactis</i>	YS	benthopelagic	0	120
140	<i>Cleisthenes pinetorum</i>	YS	demersal	50	200
141	<i>Todarodes pacificus</i>	YS	Pelagic	0	500
142	<i>Johnius belangerii</i>	YS	demersal	0	40
143	<i>Pampus argenteus</i>	YS	benthopelagic	5	110
144	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	300
145	<i>Gadus macrocephalus</i>	YS	demersal	10	1380
146	<i>Lophius litulon</i>	YS	bathydemersal	25	560
147	<i>Setipinna tenuifilis</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	50
148	<i>Conger myriaster</i>	YS	bathydemersal	65	830
149	<i>Trachurus japonicus</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	275
150	<i>Liparis tanakae</i>	YS	demersal	50	121
151	<i>Pandalus borealis</i>	YS	benthopelagic	9	1450
152	<i>Stolephorus commersonii</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	50
153	<i>Amblychaeturichthys hexanema</i>	YS	demersal	0	100
154	<i>Thryssa kammalensis</i>	YS	pelagic-neritic	0	20
155	<i>Sepia esculenta</i>	YS	benthic	10	150
156	<i>Uroteuthis chinensis</i>	YS	demersal	15	170
157	<i>Solenocera koelbeli</i>	YS	benthic	50	152

REFERENCES

- Allouche, O., Tsoar, A., Kadmon, R., 2006. Assessing the accuracy of species distribution models: prevalence, kappa and the true skill statistic (TSS): Assessing the accuracy of distribution models. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 43, 1223–1232. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2006.01214.x>
- Araújo, M.B., New, M., 2007. Ensemble forecasting of species distributions. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 22, 42–47.
- Barbet-Massin, M., Jiguet, F., Albert, C.H., Thuiller, W., 2012. Selecting pseudo-absences for species distribution models: how, where and how many? *Methods in ecology and evolution* 3, 327–338.
- Ben Rais Lasram, F., Hattab, T., Nogues, Q., Beaugrand, G., Dauvin, J.C., Halouani, G., Le Loc'h, F., Niquil, N., Leroy, B. 2020. An open-source framework to model present and future marine species distributions at local scale. *Ecological Informatics*, 2020, 59, pp.101130.
- Beaugrand, G., Lenoir, S., Ibanez, F., Manté, C., 2011. A new model to assess the probability of occurrence of a species, based on presence-only data. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 424, 175–190.
- Cushman, S.A., McGarigal, K., 2004. Patterns in the species-environment relationship depend on both scale and choice of response variables. *Oikos* 105, 117–124.
- Elith, J., H. Graham, C., P. Anderson, R., Dudík, M., Ferrier, S., Guisan, A., J. Hijmans, R., Huettmann, F., R. Leathwick, J., Lehmann, A., Li, J., G. Lohmann, L., A. Loiselle, B., Manion, G., Moritz, C., Nakamura, M., Nakazawa, Y., McC. M. Overton, J., Townsend Peterson, A., J. Phillips, S., Richardson, K., Scachetti-Pereira, R., E. Schapire, R., Soberón, J., Williams, S., S. Wisz, M., E. Zimmermann, N., 2006. Novel methods improve prediction of species' distributions from occurrence data. *Ecography* 29, 129–151. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2006.0906-7590.04596.x>
- Guisan, A., Thuiller, W., 2005. Predicting species distribution: offering more than simple habitat models. *Ecology letters* 8, 993–1009.
- Hengl, T., Sierdsema, H., Radović, A., Dilo, A., 2009. Spatial prediction of species' distributions from occurrence-only records: combining point pattern analysis, ENFA and regression-kriging. *Ecological Modelling* 220, 3499–3511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2009.06.038>
- Hirzel, A.H., Le Lay, G., Helfer, V., Randin, C., Guisan, A., 2006. Evaluating the ability of habitat suitability models to predict species presences. *ecological modelling* 199, 142–152.
- Hutchinson, G.E., 1957. *A Treatise on Limnology* 1, 243.
- Leroy, B., Delsol, R., Hugué, B., Meynard, C.N., Barhoumi, C., Barbet-Massin, M., Bellard, C., 2018. Without quality presence–absence data, discrimination metrics such as TSS can be misleading measures of model performance. *Journal of Biogeography* 45, 1994–2002.
- Morell A., Shin Y.J., Barrier N., Travers-Trolet M., Halouani G., Ernande B. Submitted, 2023. Bioen-OSMOSE: A bioenergetic marine ecosystem model with physiological responses to temperature and oxygen. *BioRxiv* <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.01.13.523601>
- Oliveros-Ramos R., Shin Y.J., Gutierrez D., Trenkel V., 2023. A multi-model selection approach for statistical downscaling and bias correction of Earth System Models outputs for regional impact applications. *BioRxiv*
- Pinsky, M.L., Worm, B., Fogarty, M.J., Sarmiento, J.L., Levin, S.A., 2013. Marine Taxa Track Local Climate Velocities. *Science* 341, 1239–1242.
- Schickele, A., Leroy, B., Beaugrand, G., Goberville, E., Hattab, T., Francour, P., Raybaud, V., 2020. Modelling European small pelagic fish distribution: Methodological insights. *Ecological Modelling* 416, 108902.
- Sunday, J., Bates, A., Dulvy, N., 2011. Global analysis of thermal tolerance and latitude in ectotherms. *Proceedings. Biological sciences / The Royal Society* 278, 1823–1830.
- Teal, L.R., Marras, S., Peck, M.A., Domenici, P., 2018. Physiology-based modelling approaches to characterize fish habitat suitability: their usefulness and limitations. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 201, 56–63.
- Thuiller, W., Brotons, L., Araújo, M.B., Lavorel, S., 2004. Effects of restricting environmental range of data to project current and future species distributions. *Ecography* 27, 165–172.

- Thuiller, W., Georges, D., Engler, R., Breiner, F., Georges, M.D., Thuiller, C.W., 2016. Package 'biomod2.' Species distribution modeling within an ensemble forecasting framework <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=biomod2>.
- Varela, S., Anderson, R.P., García-Valdés, R., Fernández-González, F., 2014. Environmental filters reduce the effects of sampling bias and improve predictions of ecological niche models. *Ecography* 37, 1084–1091.
- Woods, H.A., Moran, A.L., 2008. Oxygen profiles in egg masses predicted from a diffusion–reaction model. *Journal of Experimental Biology* 211, 790–797.